

FAMILY SUPPORT AND SELF-ESTEEM AS PREDICTORS OF RELAPSE AMONG PATIENTS WITH MENTAL ILLNESS IN KADUNA METROPOLIS, KADUNA STATE

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Abstract

*Relapse cases among mentally ill patients are a significant public health concern, with an estimated 1 in 8 people experiencing mental disorders each year. It is on this basis that this study examined family support and self-esteem as predictors of relapse among mentally ill patients in Kaduna Metropolis, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, and a total of 90 participants comprising 76 males and 14 females, with ages ranging from 16 to 70 years, participated in the study. A purposive sampling technique was used to select patients receiving care at the 44 Nigerian Army Reference Hospital Kaduna and the Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital Kaduna. Data were collected using standardized questionnaires comprising the Index of Family Relations (IFR), the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES), and the Management of Early Warning Signs of Relapse Questionnaire (MEWSReQ). Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including Pearson correlation, independent samples *t*-test, and multiple regression analysis. Four hypotheses were tested. The result of hypothesis one indicated no statistically significant difference in relapse between soldiers ($M = 39.22$) and civilian patients ($M = 38.47$), $t(88) = -0.47$, $p = .642$. The result of hypothesis two showed that family support did not significantly predict relapse ($\beta = .025$, $p = .811$). The result of hypothesis three showed that self-esteem significantly predicted relapse positively ($\beta = .396$, $p < .001$), with lower self-esteem associated with higher relapse risk. The result of hypothesis four showed that family support and self-esteem significantly predicted relapse, $F(2, 87) = 8.574$, $p < .001$; the two predictors accounted for approximately 16.5% of the variance in relapse scores. The researcher concluded that self-esteem is a critical psychosocial determinant of relapse in this population. It is recommended that mental health facilities in Kaduna incorporate a structured self-esteem intervention into the routine treatment of all patients with mental illness.*

Keywords: family support, self-esteem, relapse, mentally ill patients

Introduction

Globally, relapse cases among mentally ill patients are a significant public health concern, with an estimated 1 in 8 people experiencing mental disorders each year (World Health Organization, 2022). Conditions such as depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, and schizophrenia are prevalent worldwide, and the risk of relapse remains a critical

challenge in their management. Studies indicate that approximately 50% of individuals with major depression experience a relapse within two years of recovery, and relapse rates are even higher for disorders such as schizophrenia and bipolar disorder (Gitlin, 2006). Factors such as inadequate access to mental health services, social stigma, and the absence of continuous care contribute to these high relapse rates.

In Africa, the burden of mental illness is exacerbated by a lack of resources, cultural stigma, and insufficient mental health infrastructure. The African continent accounts for a significant portion of the global mental health burden, yet many countries in the region have limited access to mental health care, with only one psychiatrist available per million people in some areas (Sankoh et al., 2018). These limitations lead to high relapse rates, as individuals who initially receive treatment often lack the ongoing support, medication, and therapy necessary for sustained recovery. The societal stigma surrounding mental illness in many African cultures also discourages individuals from seeking help, increasing the likelihood of untreated conditions leading to relapse.

In Nigeria, mental health care faces similar challenges, with the Northern region, including Kaduna State, being particularly affected by inadequate mental health services and high relapse rates. Kaduna State, a significant state in Nigeria, has recorded a rising incidence of mental health disorders, yet the state's mental health infrastructure is insufficient to meet the growing demand (Gureje et al., 2015). Relapse cases among patients in Kaduna are often attributed to factors such as the discontinuation of treatment due to financial constraints, social stigma, and a lack of awareness about mental health. Efforts to address these issues include community-based mental health programmes and increased investment in mental health services, but the region still faces significant obstacles in reducing relapse rates and improving overall mental health outcomes.

Despite these challenges, family support plays a crucial role in the management and recovery of individuals with mental illness, significantly impacting relapse rates. Strong family support systems provide emotional stability, encouragement, and practical assistance, which are essential in helping individuals adhere to treatment plans and cope with the challenges of mental health conditions (McCann et al., 2011). Research has shown that individuals with mental illness who receive consistent family support are less likely to experience relapse, as their families often help monitor symptoms, ensure medication adherence, and offer a supportive environment conducive to recovery (Perlick et al., 2016). Conversely, a lack of family support can lead to increased stress, social isolation, and neglect of treatment, all of which contribute to higher relapse rates. Thus, the involvement of family in the care process is vital for improving long-term outcomes for individuals with mental health disorders.

Similarly, self-esteem, which is defined as an individual's overall sense of self-worth or personal value, plays a critical role in mental health and the risk of relapse in mental illness. Low self-esteem is frequently associated with various mental health disorders, including depression, anxiety, and substance abuse, as individuals with poor self-esteem may struggle with feelings of inadequacy, self-doubt, and hopelessness (Mann et al.,

2004). These negative self-perceptions can exacerbate symptoms of mental illness and hinder recovery efforts. Conversely, individuals with high self-esteem are more likely to possess resilience and coping strategies that protect against relapse. Therefore, improving self-esteem is often a key focus in therapeutic interventions for mental health disorders, as it can significantly reduce the likelihood of relapse and support sustained recovery (Sowislo & Orth, 2013).

The interplay between family support and self-esteem is crucial in understanding relapse in mental illness. Family support, which includes emotional, financial, and social assistance, provides a safety net that can significantly buffer against the challenges of mental illness. When individuals receive strong family support, they often experience higher self-esteem, as the validation and encouragement from loved ones reinforce their sense of self-worth (Corrigan & Phelan, 2004). High self-esteem, in turn, enhances resilience, enabling individuals to better cope with stressors and reducing the likelihood of relapse. Conversely, a lack of family support can erode self-esteem, leaving individuals more vulnerable to the recurrence of mental health issues. The mutual reinforcement between family support and self-esteem underscores their combined importance in preventing relapse and promoting sustained recovery in mentally ill patients (Windle et al., 2011).

Given this context, this study is crucial because it explores how these two factors may differentially impact relapse rates in military personnel compared to civilians. Soldiers often face unique stressors, such as trauma from combat or the demands of military life, which can profoundly affect their mental health and the role of family support and self-esteem in their recovery process. Understanding these dynamics could inform tailored interventions that address the specific needs of both groups, ultimately improving mental health outcomes and reducing relapse rates.

Statement of the Problem

The high rates of relapse among mentally ill patients remain a significant challenge in mental health care, with profound implications for individual well-being and public health. Relapse among patients with mental illness remains a significant challenge in Nigeria, with evidence indicating a high burden across different settings. A systematic review of African studies, including Nigeria, reported a pooled relapse prevalence of about 60.6%, suggesting that more than half of individuals with mental illness experience relapse after initial improvement (BMC Psychiatry, 2025). Nigerian hospital-based studies, particularly among patients with schizophrenia, have reported relapse rates ranging from 23% to over 70%, largely influenced by factors such as poor medication adherence, duration of illness, and inadequate social support (Bayero Journal of Nursing and Health Care, 2022). In North-Western Nigeria, a multi-centre study found marked regional variation, with Kaduna State recording a relatively lower relapse prevalence of 14% among patients with schizophrenia in 2020, compared with much higher rates in Kano and Sokoto States (Balarabe et al., 2022).

Research has consistently shown that factors such as family support and self-esteem play crucial roles in the recovery process, yet there is limited understanding of how these factors influence relapse rates, particularly when comparing distinct populations such as soldiers and civilians. Soldiers, due to the unique stressors associated with military life, may experience different dynamics in family support and self-esteem compared to civilians. However, the existing literature does not adequately address how these differences might affect the likelihood of relapse in mental illness. This gap in knowledge presents a critical issue, as effective intervention strategies may differ significantly between these two groups. Therefore, it is essential to investigate how family support and self-esteem predict relapse in mentally ill patients, with a focus on the comparative impact between soldiers and civilians. Addressing this problem will not only enhance our understanding of relapse predictors but also inform the development of tailored interventions aimed at reducing relapse rates and improving long-term mental health outcomes in these populations.

Research Questions

The following questions guided this study:

1. What is the difference in relapse between soldiers and civilian patients suffering from mental illness in Kaduna Metropolis?
2. How does family support influence relapse among mentally ill patients in Kaduna Metropolis?
3. How does self-esteem predict relapse among mentally ill patients in Kaduna Metropolis?
4. How do family support and self-esteem jointly influence relapse among mentally ill patients in Kaduna Metropolis?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to investigate the role of family support and self-esteem as predictors of relapse among mentally ill patients. Specifically, the following objectives were investigated:

1. Determine whether there is a significant difference in relapse between soldiers and civilian patients suffering from mental illness in Kaduna Metropolis.
2. Assess the extent to which family support significantly influences relapse among mentally ill patients in Kaduna Metropolis.
3. Examine the extent to which self-esteem significantly predicts relapse among mentally ill patients in Kaduna Metropolis.
4. Investigate the joint influence of family support and self-esteem on relapse among mentally ill patients in Kaduna Metropolis.

Hypotheses

The study postulated the following hypotheses:

1. There will be a significant difference in relapse between soldiers and civilian patients suffering from mental illness in Kaduna Metropolis.
2. Family support will significantly influence relapse among mentally ill patients in Kaduna Metropolis.
3. Self-esteem will significantly predict relapse among mentally ill patients in Kaduna Metropolis.
4. Family support and self-esteem will jointly have a significant influence on relapse among mentally ill patients in Kaduna Metropolis.

Methods

Design

A cross-sectional design was employed in this study. This is a research method that involves collecting data from a specific population or a representative subset at one point in time. It allows researchers to examine the relationships between different variables without manipulating them, making it useful for identifying patterns, correlations, and potential associations between factors. This design is cost-effective and efficient for capturing a snapshot of a population, though it does not allow for the establishment of causal relationships.

Setting

The setting of this study is Kaduna Metropolis, a major urban center in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Kaduna is one of the largest cities in Northern Nigeria, serving as a political, cultural, and economic hub in the region. The metropolis is characterized by a diverse population with various ethnic groups, religions, and socioeconomic backgrounds. The city is home to both civilian and military populations, as it hosts several military institutions, including the Nigerian Defence Academy (NDA) and other military formations, making it an ideal location for comparative studies involving both civilian and military personnel.

Kaduna Metropolis provides an appropriate setting for this study because it uniquely accommodates both a large military population and a diverse civilian population within the same urban environment. The metropolis, which includes Kaduna North, Kaduna South, Chikun, and parts of Igabi, hosts major military formations such as the Nigerian Defence Academy and 1 Division Nigerian Army, where soldiers are often exposed to occupational stressors, strict command structures, and frequent separation from family, factors that may weaken family support and self-esteem and increase relapse risk. In contrast, civilian patients largely rely on family-based care and community support systems, which are influenced by socioeconomic conditions, stigma, and family cohesion. Examining both soldiers and civilians in Kaduna Metropolis allows for a comparative understanding of how family support and self-esteem predict relapse within differing social and occupational contexts.

In this study, mentally ill patients were recruited from 44 Nigerian Army Reference Hospital Kaduna (NARHK) and Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital (FNPH) Kaduna. These facilities provide services to both civilian and military populations, allowing for the examination of the research variables, that is, family support, self-esteem, and relapse, in different groups. The city's healthcare infrastructure includes both public and private mental health services, providing a range of care for individuals with various mental health conditions. The inclusion of both military and civilian mental health patients in the study is particularly significant, as it allows for a comparative analysis of how these two groups experience mental health challenges and how family support and self-esteem contribute to mental illness relapse in the Kaduna Metropolis context.

Participants

The participants of this study were mentally ill patients receiving treatment at the 44 Nigerian Army Reference Hospital (NARHK) and the Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital Kaduna (FNPHK) in Kaduna Metropolis. The study included both civilian and soldier patients receiving treatment at the two facilities.

Inclusion Criteria

Participants were included in the study if they met the following conditions:

1. Had been formally diagnosed with a mental illness by a qualified mental health professional.
2. Had experienced at least one episode of relapse in the past.
3. Were currently receiving treatment as inpatients or outpatients at either 44 NARHK or FNPHK.
4. Were willing and able to provide informed consent or assent, where applicable.

Exclusion Criteria

Participants were excluded from the study if they:

1. Had no history of relapse.
2. Were experiencing an acute psychotic episode that impaired their ability to provide reliable responses.
3. Had severe cognitive impairment or intellectual disability that would hinder comprehension of the questionnaire.
4. Declined to participate or withdrew consent during the study.

The sample comprised 90 participants drawn from two major psychiatric facilities in Kaduna Metropolis. The majority were male ($n = 76$, 84.4%), with only 14 females (15.6%), reflecting the predominantly male composition of the patients included in the study. In terms of age, most participants fell within the 31-45 years bracket ($n = 42$, 46.7%), followed by the 16-30 age group ($n = 37$, 41.1%), with the smallest proportion being those aged 46-70 years ($n = 11$, 12.2%). The sample was nearly evenly split between Muslims ($n = 49$, 54.4%) and Christians ($n = 41$, 45.6%). Regarding educational

attainment, over half of the participants held tertiary-level qualifications ($n = 47, 52.2\%$), and the majority were employed ($n = 54, 60.0\%$). More than half of the participants were single ($n = 47, 52.2\%$), while 42.2% were married. The sample consisted of slightly more civilians ($n = 49, 54.4\%$) than soldiers ($n = 41, 45.6\%$). With respect to psychiatric diagnosis, depression was the most common diagnosis ($n = 31, 34.4\%$), followed by schizophrenia ($n = 23, 25.6\%$) and Substance Use Disorder ($n = 15, 16.7\%$), with PTSD, bipolar disorder, seizures, and dementia accounting for the remaining cases.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The target population for this study consisted of mentally ill patients admitted to the 44 Nigerian Army Reference Hospital (NARHK) and the Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital Kaduna (FNPHK) in Kaduna Metropolis, with an estimated combined population of approximately 400 patients. The sample size for this study was determined based on Green's (1991) recommendation for multiple regression analysis. Green suggested a minimum sample size of $N > 50 + 8k$, where k represents the number of predictors in the model. With two independent variables, family support and self-esteem, in the multiple regression, the minimum required sample size is 66 participants.

From the population, 105 participants were selected using a purposive sampling technique. A total of 105 questionnaires were administered and retrieved. After screening, 15 questionnaires were excluded due to incomplete responses or improper filling, resulting in a final sample of 90 participants. The final sample of 90 exceeds this threshold, providing adequate statistical power to examine the predictive roles of family support and self-esteem on relapse.

Instruments

The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire comprising four sections as follows:

Section A—Demographic Data: This section consisted of eight items covering the following variables: gender, religion, age, level of education, occupation, marital status, professional status, and diagnosis.

Section B—Index of Family Relations: The Index of Family Relations (IFR) was developed by Hudson (1982). The IFR is a standardized self-report instrument designed to measure the quality of interpersonal relationships within the family system, particularly the extent of support, cohesion, and conflict experienced by an individual within their family environment. The scale conceptualizes family relationships along a continuum ranging from healthy, supportive, and cohesive interactions to distressed, conflictual, and dysfunctional patterns (Hudson, 1982).

The IFR consists of 25 items that assess respondents' perceptions of their family relationships. Items are rated on a Likert-type scale, typically ranging from "rarely or none of the time" to "most or all of the time." The instrument includes both positively and negatively worded items reflecting dimensions such as emotional closeness,

communication, support, and conflict within the family. Negatively worded items are reverse scored, and all responses are summed to yield a total score. Higher scores indicate greater levels of family distress, which in the context of the present study implies lower perceived family support, whereas lower scores reflect healthier and more supportive family relationships (Hudson, 1982).

The IFR has demonstrated strong psychometric properties. Hudson (1982) reported a high level of internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of approximately .95, indicating excellent reliability. The scale has also shown good construct validity through its associations with related measures of psychological functioning and interpersonal adjustment. Its ability to discriminate between clinical and non-clinical populations further supports its validity as a measure of family relational problems (Hudson, 1982).

Given its robust psychometric properties, the IFR is particularly suitable for this study, as it provides a reliable and valid means of examining how family support contributes to self-esteem and relapse among mentally ill patients within the military and civilian populations in Kaduna Metropolis.

Section C—Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES): The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES) was developed by Rosenberg (1965). It is a widely used psychometric instrument designed to assess an individual's self-esteem. The scale has become a standard measure in psychological research due to its simplicity, reliability, and validity. The RSES focuses on global self-esteem, capturing both positive and negative feelings about oneself, making it particularly relevant for studies exploring the relationship between self-esteem and mental health outcomes, including relapse in mentally ill patients. The RSES consists of 10 statements that respondents rate on a four-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree." Five of the items are positively phrased (e.g., "I take a positive attitude toward myself"), while the other five are negatively phrased (e.g., "At times, I think I am no good at all"). The scores are summed, with higher total scores indicating lower self-esteem. This straightforward format makes the RSES easy to administer and interpret in both clinical and research settings.

The RSES has demonstrated excellent reliability, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients typically exceeding 0.90, indicating high internal consistency (Rosenberg, 1965). Test-retest reliability studies also show stability over time, confirming that the scale produces consistent results across different administrations. In terms of validity, the RSES has been shown to correlate significantly with other established measures of self-esteem and related constructs, such as life satisfaction and depression (Crocker et al., 2003). Numerous studies have affirmed its construct validity, establishing a robust relationship between self-esteem levels and various mental health outcomes, including anxiety and depressive symptoms (Sowislo & Orth, 2013). The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale is a valuable tool for assessing self-esteem and its implications for mental health. Its strong reliability and validity make it an ideal instrument for this study, particularly in examining the predictive role of self-esteem on relapse among mentally ill patients in Kaduna Metropolis.

Section D—Management of Early Warning Signs of Relapse Questionnaire

(MEWSRQ): The Management of Early Warning Signs of Relapse Questionnaire (MEWSRQ) was developed and validated by Abu-Sabra (2023) to measure relapse risk and related self-management abilities among mentally ill patients. It is an adapted self-report questionnaire specifically designed to assess patients' and caregivers' ability to identify early warning signs of relapse, employ coping mechanisms, and reflect on relapse history, thereby supporting early intervention and relapse prevention in psychiatric care.

The MEWSRQ consists of 15 items divided into three theoretically derived subscales of five items each:

1. Early Warning Signs (items 1-5)—assesses changes in mood, behaviour, sleep, motivation, and physical symptoms that may signal impending relapse.
2. Coping Mechanisms (items 6-10)—evaluates the use of proactive strategies such as having a management plan, practising stress-reduction techniques, utilising social support, challenging negative thoughts, and engaging in physical activity.
3. Relapse History (items 11-15)—explores past relapse experiences, identification of triggers, history of hospitalisation, distress or impairment, and family history of mental health conditions.

Respondents rate each item on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree. The questionnaire is straightforward, self-administered, and suitable for both clinical and research settings with mentally ill populations. Subscale scores are obtained by summing the five items in each domain (range: 5-25 per subscale). The total score is the sum of all 15 items, ranging from 15 (minimum) to 75 (maximum). Higher scores on the Early Warning Signs and Relapse History subscales indicate greater relapse risk, while higher scores on the Coping Mechanisms subscale reflect stronger protective factors. For the purpose of this study, a composite relapse-risk total was computed by reversing the Coping Mechanisms subscale and adding it to the Early Warning Signs and Relapse History subscales. This ensures that higher overall risk scores consistently reflect greater vulnerability to relapse, aligning with the instrument's clinical interpretation guidelines (Abu-Sabra, 2023). The MEWSRQ demonstrates strong psychometric properties. The original validation study reported excellent internal consistency alpha ($\alpha = 0.92$) and satisfactory construct validity, confirming its suitability for assessing self-management of early warning signs in individuals with mental illness.

Procedure

The researcher first obtained a letter of introduction from the Department of Psychology, Nigerian Defence Academy (NDA), which was used to apply for ethical approval from the ethical committees of the Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital Kaduna (FNPHK) and the 44 Nigerian Army Reference Hospital Kaduna (44 NARHK). Ethical approval was obtained from both institutions before the commencement of data collection. Following approval, participants were recruited from the two selected mental health facilities within Kaduna Metropolis, namely FNPHK and 44 NARHK. Collaboration with mental health

professionals and administrative staff in these facilities facilitated the identification of eligible participants who met the inclusion criteria, specifically patients diagnosed with a mental illness and with a history of at least one relapse episode.

A purposive sampling technique was employed to recruit participants who met the study criteria. Recruitment was carried out within the clinical settings, and potential participants were approached with the assistance of healthcare personnel. The study included both soldiers and civilian patients receiving care in the selected facilities. Participation was voluntary, and no strict proportional allocation was imposed across any groups; rather, inclusion was based on eligibility and willingness to participate. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants. Each participant was provided with an information sheet detailing the purpose of the study, procedures involved, potential risks and benefits, and their rights, including the right to withdraw at any time without consequences. The consent form was presented in clear and simple language to ensure comprehension, and participants were given the opportunity to ask questions before providing written consent. Only those who consented voluntarily were included in the study.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire comprising three standardized instruments: the Index of Family Relations (IFR) for assessing family support, the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES) for measuring self-esteem, and the Management of Early Warning Signs of Relapse Questionnaire (MEWSReQ) for assessing relapse vulnerability. The instruments were administered in a quiet and conducive environment within the facilities to ensure privacy and minimize distractions. Two trained research assistants assisted in administering the questionnaires and provided clarification where necessary to enhance accurate responses.

A total of 105 questionnaires were administered; upon retrieval, the questionnaires were screened for completeness and accuracy. Fifteen questionnaires were excluded due to incomplete or improper responses, resulting in a final sample of 90 valid cases used for analysis. The collected data were coded and entered into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 26.0, for analysis. All responses were anonymized to ensure confidentiality. Each participant was assigned a unique identification number, which enabled data tracking without revealing personal identities.

Method of Data Analysis

Data analysis for this study involved both descriptive and inferential statistical methods to examine the relationships between family support, self-esteem, and relapse risk among mentally ill patients. Initially, descriptive statistics were computed to summarize the demographic characteristics of the participants, including age, gender, and related variables. Following the descriptive analysis, inferential statistics were employed to test the study's hypotheses. Independent samples t-tests were conducted to test hypothesis one, which explored differences in relapse risk between civilian and soldier participants. Correlation analyses were conducted to test hypotheses two and three, which assessed the relationships between family support, self-esteem, and relapse risk. Multiple regression analysis was performed to test hypothesis four, which evaluated the predictive

roles of family support and self-esteem on relapse risk, allowing for the examination of the unique contributions of each variable. All statistical tests were conducted at a significance level of $p < .05$, and effect sizes were reported to determine the practical significance of the findings.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to strict ethical considerations to ensure the protection and well-being of participants. Some of the ethical considerations include:

1. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and the study’s purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits were clearly explained.
2. Participants’ confidentiality and anonymity were safeguarded by coding data and securely storing it.
3. Voluntary participation ensured that the study avoided any form of coercion, with the right to withdraw at any time without repercussions.
4. Ethical approval was obtained from the ethical committees of FNPHK and 44 NARHK, in compliance with ethical guidelines for research involving vulnerable populations.
5. Benevolence and risk management were employed to ensure that care was taken to minimize emotional distress by providing access to mental health support if needed during or after participation.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1
Demographic Characteristics of Participants (N = 90)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	76	84.4
Female	14	15.6
Total	90	100%
Age Group		
16-30 years	37	41.1
31-45 years	42	46.7
46-70 years	11	12.2
Total	90	100%

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Religion		
Christianity	41	45.6
Islam	49	54.4
Total	90	100%
Level of Education		
Primary	3	3.3
Secondary	40	44.4
Tertiary	47	52.2
Total	90	100%
Occupation		
None	5	5.6
Student	13	14.4
Employee	54	60.0
Private Business	18	20.0
Total	90	100%
Marital Status		
Single	47	52.2
Married	38	42.2
Divorced	4	4.4
Widowed	1	1.1
Total	90	100%
Participant Status		
Civilian	49	54.4
Soldier	41	45.6
Total	90	100%
Psychiatric Diagnosis		
Seizures	5	5.6

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
PTSD	7	7.8
Bipolar Disorder	8	8.9
Substance Use Disorder (SUD)	15	16.7
Schizophrenia	23	25.6
Dementia	1	1.1
Depression	31	34.4
Total	90	100%

Note. N = 90. SUD = Substance Use Disorder; PTSD = Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder.

The sample comprised 90 participants drawn from two major psychiatric facilities in Kaduna Metropolis. The majority were male (n = 76, 84.4%), with only 14 females (15.6%), reflecting the predominantly male composition of the patients included in the study. In terms of age, most participants fell within the 31-45 years bracket (n = 42, 46.7%), followed by the 16-30 age group (n = 37, 41.1%), with the smallest proportion being those aged 46-70 years (n = 11, 12.2%). The sample was nearly evenly split between Muslims (n = 49, 54.4%) and Christians (n = 41, 45.6%). Regarding educational attainment, over half of the participants held tertiary-level qualifications (n = 47, 52.2%), and the majority were employed (n = 54, 60.0%). More than half of the participants were single (n = 47, 52.2%), while 42.2% were married. The sample consisted of slightly more civilians (n = 49, 54.4%) than soldiers (n = 41, 45.6%). With respect to psychiatric diagnosis, depression was the most common diagnosis (n = 31, 34.4%), followed by schizophrenia (n = 23, 25.6%) and Substance Use Disorder (n = 15, 16.7%), with PTSD, bipolar disorder, seizures, and dementia accounting for the remaining cases.

This section presents the means, standard deviations, and intercorrelations among all study variables, including demographic variables and the three primary study variables: family support, self-esteem, and relapse.

Table 4.1
Means, Standard Deviations, Correlations

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1. Gender	1.16	.36	-										
2. Religion	1.54	.50	-.16	-									
3. Age	1.71	.67	.14	-.13	-								
4. Education	2.49	.57	.12	-.04	-.04	-							
5. Occupation	2.94	.76	-.05	-.13	.03	-.02	-						

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
6. Marital Status	1.54	.64	.02	.12	.53**	-.09	.09	-					